

PACIFICUS

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“OUTBURST OF BEAUTY”

Once a duckling in the marsh,
Now a swan in the lake.
Then, craven and vulnerable,
Now, intrepid yet humble.

Strong cold wind passes by,
In the pond she swam with lullaby,
Making such wings sturdy
With each blow no matter how heavy.

Valiant even with rosary pea
Offered by a turkey,
Never will she yield,
Trusting faith as her shield.

The duckling you once taunted
In the marsh you yourself created,
Now sending shivers in your spine
As her wings spread in purest white.

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